

Original Article

From Waste to Utility: Recycled PET as a 3D Printing Material in Dentistry: An *In vitro* Study

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The overuse of plastics in the past decade raised significant global concerns, prompting a shift toward sustainable materials to mitigate plastic consumption. Among these efforts, recycling post-consumer plastic waste has emerged as a critical focus area. This study aimed to explore the potential of post-consumer recycled polyethylene terephthalate (PCR rPET) as a sustainable alternative to virgin plastics, focusing on the development of a novel 3D printable filament for dental applications. Two types of PCR rPET pellets were collected from commercially available sources in India, one was made from processed plastic waste and directly made to pellets (PCR rPET-d). The other pellets had undergone additional solid-state polymerization (SSP) to increase their density and extrudability (PCR rPET-s). Material characterization was conducted for both the test materials using Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), and melt flow index (MFI) testing. A sample size of 10 was used for these analyses. Subsequently, the pellets were extruded into 1.75 mm diameter filament using a traditional twin-screw extruder. The filament extrudability was recorded by observing the rate of flow while extrusion and measuring the diameter of resultant filament. The data were analysed using descriptive statistics to identify trends and assess the material's suitability for dental applications, including model preparation, surgical guides, temporary prostheses, and custom trays. The PCR rPET-s material showed promising extrudability and filament production potential. However, challenges such as excessive flow and uneven heating during extrusion resulted in a narrow filament diameter of 1.2mm (\pm 0.05 mm). PCR rPET-d, showed blackening and bubbling while extruding making it unsuitable. Despite the challenges encountered, PCR rPET-s demonstrated considerable potential as a sustainable alternative in dental prosthesis fabrication. Further optimization of extrusion parameters and equipment design is needed to improve filament consistency and quality. This research highlights the importance of future advancements in sustainable manufacturing techniques by optimizing extrusion processes for broader applications.

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Introduction

The growing concerns over plastic pollution have intensified in recent years, leading to an urgent global call for sustainable alternatives to traditional petroleum-based plastics. In particular, single-use plastics, which have proliferated due to their convenience and low cost, have had an unprecedented impact on the environment, contributing to pollution in oceans, rivers, and landfills. According to the United Nations, over 300 million tons of plastic are produced annually, with a significant portion of this waste generated by the packaging industry [1]. This trend has placed

immense pressure on the development of recycling technologies and sustainable materials to curb plastic waste and reduce its harmful impact.

Among the potential solutions to plastic pollution, post-consumer recycled (PCR) plastics have gained significant attention as a sustainable alternative to virgin plastics. Recycling post-consumer materials reduces the reliance on non-renewable resources, limits environmental contamination, and decreases energy consumption associated with the production of virgin plastics. Post-consumer recycled polyethylene terephthalate (PCR rPET) is a promising candidate for such applications due to its durability, ease of recycling, and widespread use in products like beverage bottles and packaging [2]. However, challenges in processing and quality control remain, particularly when recycled plastics are used in high-precision applications such as 3D printing [3].

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In the field of dentistry, 3D printing has revolutionized the production of dental prosthetics, including crowns, bridges, implants, and surgical guides, by offering precise customization and reduced production times [4]. Dental 3D printing technologies typically rely on materials like acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS), photopolymer resins, and polyethylene terephthalate glycol (PET-G), which are derived from virgin plastics. These materials, while offering high precision and durability, also contribute to environmental degradation due to their non-renewable origins. The potential of recycled plastics, particularly PCR rPET, as a sustainable alternative in dental applications, remains largely unexplored. The ability to develop a 3D printable filament from PCR rPET could reduce the environmental footprint of dental prosthesis fabrication while maintaining the material properties necessary for accurate and durable medical applications.

Currently, PCR rPET is used in various industries, including the automotive sector, food packaging and fabric production. However, its application in 3D printing, requires further exploration. A major challenge in using recycled materials for 3D printing lies in ensuring the material's extrudability, consistency in filament diameter, and overall print quality. The extrusion process itself can introduce variability in the filament's physical properties, including its diameter, which is crucial for maintaining the quality and precision of the printed object [5]. Furthermore, the recyclability and sustainability of PCR rPET depend not only on its chemical and physical properties but also on its processing parameters, which must be optimized for specific applications.

The purpose of this study was to evaluate PCR rPET as a sustainable alternative to virgin plastics in dental 3D printing applications. The focus of the research is on developing a novel 3D printable filament from PCR rPET and assessing its suitability for dental prosthesis fabrication. Through material characterization, extrusion, and filament production, this study aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the potential and challenges of using PCR rPET for dental 3D printing.

The findings from this study contribute valuable data on the feasibility of using PCR rPET in dental 3D printing, with implications for reducing plastic waste and fostering sustainable manufacturing practices. By evaluating the material's performance and identifying the challenges that must be overcome, this research could open the door to more sustainable dental prosthesis production in the future.

Materials and Methods

Collection of samples

Commercially available food contact grade, FSSAI-approved, post-consumer recycled PET pellets were obtained. The PCR plastic was processed by collection, segregation, cutting, washing, and drying before extruding them into pellets, such pellets were collected and grouped as PCR rPET-d. later, rPET further underwent a process called solid state polymerization (SSP) to improve its internal viscosity (IV) which reflected in its crystallinity, density, and extrudability [6]. This group is labeled as PCR rPET-s, it showed an IV of 0.8 dl/g while, PCR rPET-d group had an IV of 0.7 dl/g

Comprehensive material characterization is essential to evaluating the performance of post-consumer recycled polyethylene terephthalate (PCR rPET) as a 3D printing material. This includes analyzing the material's chemical structure, thermal properties, and flow behavior to ensure its suitability for extrusion and subsequent use in dental 3D printing applications.

Chemical Structure Analysis

Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) was used to evaluate the chemical integrity of PCR rPET. FTIR is a powerful analytical tool used to investigate the molecular structure of PCR rPET. It provides critical insights into the functional groups and chemical bonds within the polymer. Additionally, it helps identify any degradation or contamination that might have occurred during the recycling process, such as hydrolysis or oxidation of the polymer chains. For instance, the presence of carbonyl peaks in the spectrum may indicate degradation from repeated processing cycles [7]. This analysis is vital for ensuring that the recycled material retains the necessary chemical integrity for use in dental applications.

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

DSC measures the heat flow associated with phase transitions in PCR rPET, such as glass transition (T_g), crystallization, and melting points. These thermal properties determine the material's ability to flow and solidify during extrusion and 3D printing. Recycled PET often exhibits changes in crystallinity due to processing, which can affect its mechanical properties and printability. Understanding these transitions ensures proper optimization of printing parameters.

Melt flow index (MFI)

The MFI test is used to quantify the flowability of PCR rPET under specific temperature and load conditions. A higher MFI indicates better flow properties, which are critical for producing a consistent filament with minimal interruptions. Recycled PET may have altered flow properties due to molecular weight changes, making this analysis essential to predict extrusion behavior.

Filament production

Extruding PCR rPET into a consistent, high-quality filament is a fundamental step in developing a 3D printable material. In this study, a traditional twin-screw extruder was employed to convert PCR rPET pellets into filament with a standard diameter of 1.75 mm, widely used in fused deposition modeling (FDM) 3D printers. Variations in diameter can lead to under- or over-extrusion during printing, adversely affecting the dimensional accuracy of the printed object [8]. Therefore, it is carefully measured using an inbuilt calibration feature of the extruder.

Results and Discussion

Chemical structure analysis

Both FTIR spectra (refer to figures 1A and 1B) confirm PET as the primary component, identifiable by key ester and aromatic functional group peaks. A strong peak around $1710-1715\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponds to the C=O stretch of the ester carbonyl group, while peaks at $2920-2950\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $2850-2860\text{ cm}^{-1}$ represent C-H stretching vibrations of CH₂ groups. Vibrations from the aromatic ring appear at $1400-1500\text{ cm}^{-1}$, and C-O stretching of ester groups is observed at $1090-1250\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in both spectra [9]. However, differences between the two samples are notable. The PCR rPET-s spectrum exhibits sharper peaks, indicating higher crystallinity or purity compared to PCR rPET-d. A weak, broad peak in the $3600-3800\text{ cm}^{-1}$ range in PCR rPET-s suggests O-H stretching, likely from moisture or hydroxyl groups, which is less visible in PCR rPET-d. Meanwhile, PCR rPET-d shows a minor peak around 420 cm^{-1} , absent in PCR rPET-s, possibly indicating residual impurities or minor functional groups. Importantly, neither spectrum shows significant peaks for degradation products, such as carbonyl oxidation, confirming the preservation of polymer integrity during recycling. This aligns with ISO 10640, ensuring chemical consistency for functional applications.

Figure 1: FTIR test results of (A) PCR rPET-d and (B) PCR rPET-s

Differential scanning calorimetry (DSC)

DSC analysis, as per ISO 11357-1, confirms the thermal stability of PCR rPET for high-temperature applications like dental 3D printing [10]. The study, conducted on 5 g samples heated at 15°C/min from 0–300°C, highlighted clear differences in thermal behavior. PCR rPET-s (refer to figure 2A) showed a sharp melting peak at 239.54°C, with an onset at 234.22°C and a normalized enthalpy of

Figure 2: DSC test results of (A) PCR rPET-d and (B) PCR rPET-s

Figure 3: (A) Ideal flow of virgin PET g and (B) Increased flow of PCR rPET-d

24.957 J/g, indicating high crystallinity and thermal stability. On the other hand, PCR rPET-d (refer to figure 2B) displayed a more complex profile with a glass transition at 74.84°C, crystallization at 133.64°C, and a broader melting range of 221.31–263.22°C with a higher enthalpy of 30.2387 J/g. This suggests PCR rPET-d is semi-crystalline, combining both amorphous and crystalline phases.

Melt flow index (MFI)

Based on the thermal behaviors observed in the DSC test results, the Melt Flow Index (MFI) test was conducted in accordance with the ASTM D1238 standard. For PCR rPET-d samples, 200 g of material was heated to 250°C, and the flow was measured under a 2.16 kg load. The MFI values obtained ranged from 7.17 to 7.3 g/10 min. In contrast, for PCR rPET-s samples, the test was performed at a temperature of 285°C with a load of 5 kg, resulting in MFI values ranging from 9.2 to 9.7 g/10 min. The test results suggest the potential extrudability of PCR rPET-s, but in case of PCR rPET-d, there may be an excess flow that can hinder filament production.

Filament production

PCR rPET-d filament extrusion

Filament extrusion was attempted using a conventional twin-screw extruder, with the heating temperature set to 220°C to mitigate excessive flow. During the process, the material exhibited signs of uneven heating, discoloration (turning black), bubbling, and evidence of thermal degradation (refer to figures 3A and 3B). Attempts to optimize the process by adjusting screw speed and reducing the temperature resulted in inadequate heating, which prevented continuous extrusion. These findings indicate that the material is inherently unsuitable for extrusion applications under the tested conditions.

Figure 4: (A) Continuous extrusion with increased flow seen in PCR rPET-s extrusion and (B) PCR rPET-s filament obtained

PCR rPET-s filament extrusion

Filament extrusion of this material resulted in a successful continuous filament production process (refer to figure 4A). However, the resultant filament exhibited significant diameter variation along its length, deviating from the ideal 1.75 mm diameter. This variation is likely attributable to the increased flow properties of the recycled material compared to virgin PET-G. The obtained filament (refer to figure 4B) had an average diameter of 1.2mm (\pm 0.05 mm). Therefore, further optimization of extrusion parameters and cooling systems is required to enhance the consistency and quality of the filament production process.

Conclusion

The study demonstrated the potential of post-consumer recycled polyethylene terephthalate (PCR rPET) as a sustainable alternative to virgin plastics in dental 3D printing applications. PCR rPET exhibited promising thermal stability, molecular integrity, and extrudability, though challenges such as uneven filament diameter and brittleness were observed. Addressing these issues through optimization of extrusion parameters and material modifications will enhance its applicability. Future research should focus on improving filament consistency, incorporating impact modifiers, and evaluating mechanical properties of 3D-printed dental products. Expanding its applications can contribute significantly to sustainable manufacturing and reducing plastic pollution in healthcare industries.

This study focuses on improving the extrusion process to maximize the quality of PCR rPET filament. Future work will explore advanced cooling techniques and the addition of stabilizers to further enhance the filament's uniformity and mechanical properties,

ensuring its suitability for high-precision dental applications such as surgical guides, temporary prostheses, and custom trays.

References

1. Everything you need to know about plastic pollution (2022) UNEP. Available at: <https://www.unep.org/news-and-stories/story/everything-you-need-know-about-plastic-pollution> (2022).
2. Benyathiar, P. et al. Polyethylene terephthalate (PET) bottle-to-bottle recycling for the beverage industry: A Review, *Polymers*, 14(12), 2366 (2022).
3. Maraveas, C., Kyrtpoulos, I.V. and Arvanitis, K.G. Evaluation of the viability of 3D printing in recycling polymers, *Polymers*, 16(8), 1104 (2024).
4. Tian, Y. et al. A review of 3D printing in Dentistry: Technologies, affecting factors, and applications', *Scanning*, 2021, 1–19 (2021).
5. Ponsar, H., Wiedey, R. and Quodbach, J. Hot-melt extrusion process fluctuations and their impact on critical quality attributes of filaments and 3D-printed dosage forms, *Pharmaceutics*, 12(6), 511 (2020).
6. Frounchi, M. Studies on degradation of PET in mechanical recycling, *Macromolecular Symposia*, 144(1), 465–469 (1999).
7. Van de Voorde, B. et al. Effect of extrusion and fused filament fabrication processing parameters of recycled poly(ethylene terephthalate) on the crystallinity and mechanical properties', *Additive Manufacturing*, 50, 102518 (2022).
8. Cardona, C., Curdes, A.H. and Isaacs, A.J. Effects of filament diameter tolerances in fused filament fabrication, *IU Journal of Undergraduate Research*, 2(1), 44–47 (2016).
9. Soong, Y.-H.V., Sobkiewicz, M.J. and Xie, D. Recent advances in biological recycling of polyethylene terephthalate (PET) plastic wastes, *Bioengineering*, 9(3), 98 (2016).
10. Šudomová, L. et al. A differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) approach for assessing the quality of polyethylene terephthalate (PET) waste for physical recycling: A proof-of-concept study, *Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry*, 148(20), 10843–10855 (2023).